

24/7 CLEAN ENERGY SUPPLY FOR CERN

End of project compendium

March 29th 2023 (V7.0)

Executive summary

With the construction of the FCC, CERN annual consumption is expected to increase from ~1.2 TWh today up to 2.6 TWh p.a. in ~2055-2060 with variation from 1.1 TWh to 2.6 TWh per year between 2045 and 2065. About ~70-75% of the energy will be used for the FCC with an hourly profile varying from 85 MWh to 472 MWh

CERN main focus is to supply FCC with affordable energy while limiting large uncertainties on price and meeting commonly accepted criteria for “green power supply”

Offshore wind has been identified as a key technology for CERN for power supply, to be procured “investment-alike” via a PPA pre-FID supporting the development of a new offshore wind park located in France, with a partner who makes the capital investment and carries the construction & operational risks. CERN would enable the construction of an offshore wind farm larger than its needs for the FCC-ee (such as a 1 GW project for approximately a need between 230 MW and 530 MW for the FCC-ee).

The energy cost (pure electricity cost excluding taxes, transmission and distribution costs) for CERN is estimated to be between 43 and 78 EUR/MWh– a range accounting for uncertainties in Capex and market price – in real economic terms of today (2023). This cost includes the sourcing price of PPAs, and adjustments needed on the grid to match CERN’s profile. This could be a very attractive energy price and would reduce financial risk substantially.

Each year, CERN would buy from the offshore wind project at least the total amount of power required. However, buying from the grid would still be necessary in some hours when CERN’s demand is higher than the contracted renewable power production. This is more likely to be during more expensive hours (i.e., when overall renewable power production is low). Similarly, selling to the grid would be required in other hours when CERN’s demand is lower than the contracted renewable power production. This is more likely to be during hours when market prices are the lowest (i.e., when overall renewable power production is high). These risks, called profile risks, could be managed by a 3rd party or the PPA provider.

Agenda

Key objectives and solution space

Demand overview

Assessment of options

Societal impact

Appendix

Cost stability and affordability are CERN's main focus when procuring energy for the FCC

1. nuclear energy could be indirectly included through buying from the grid

Procuring clean power can be defined across 3 dimensions

Overview of potential solution space

Not considered as part of solution space

B How is power procured?

Dimensions	Rational for exclusion from assessment
Hydro	Limited possibilities of new build-out
Geothermal	Limited availability at scale and future economics highly uncertain
Nuclear	Not considered as green by some state members
Biomass	Not available at scale (5-60MW plant) Renewable source (e.g., wood) however emitting CO2 and often not considered green
On-site solar	Expected limited capacity vs total need
Switzerland	Expected limited additional capacity

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CERN consumption during the FCC-ee period 2045-2065

Sample years for supply optimization
 Focus of this effort
 Preveessin sites
 Meyrin site
 LHC
 FCC

Expected annual power consumption, TWh

Hourly demand profile derived from yearly operation schedule and machine cycles

■ Beam operation
 ■ Machine development
 ■ Commissioning
 ■ Technical stop
 ■ Shut down

Methodology and assumptions

FCC is scheduled to operate in different modes during a year, including beam operation, machine development, commissioning, technical stop and shutdown

Each operation mode is represented by different cycles of machine stages, with varied power demand

The hourly profile is created by defining the standard machine cycles, and afterwards assigning those cycles to periods of operations

Only hourly change are considered

Only standard cycles are considered, without simulating occasional system failures

Meyrin and Preveessin sites are modeled as flat load for each operation mode

Assumed profiles for CERN during Z operation, MW

Weekly max load profile

Hourly load profile (extract)

Total demand is composed of 3 blocks – FCC, Meyrin and Preveessin

Sample hourly demand load profile from 27/05 to 28/05

■ Focus of the modelization

Weekly profiles for the FCC are expected to be similar in the 4 operation phases

■ Beam operation
 ■ Machine development
 ■ Commissioning
 ■ Technical stop
 ■ Shut down

Weekly load profile during Z operation, MW

Weekly load profile during W operation, MW

Weekly load profile during H operation, MW

Weekly load profile during TT operation, MW

For the FCC, an hourly load profile is defined by machine schedule and operation type

— Z — W — H — TT

Machine schedule	Beam operation	Machine development	Commissioning	Technical stop	Shutdown
Description	When the beam is stable and in collision for experiments. 100% RF power is reached on average twice 8h over the 24h with some downtime	Planned activities with beam operation to improve the beam operation without physics production (10-20% of RF power)	The period before beam operation where all systems are restarted and tested (RF power at 0% except ~10% in TT operation)	Planned stops during beam operation to perform maintenance and repairs, last 5 consecutive days	The machine is stopped and open for work, maintenance, and repair activities (currently scheduled in winter when electricity is more expensive)

Illustrative hourly profile, MW

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Technology mix

- Procurement options
- Geography

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Technology mix summary (1/2)

Based on cost assumptions and the expected hourly load profile of CERN, a linear optimization was done to identify the cost-optimal technology mix – assuming the RES portfolio would generate at least the energy required by CERN on a yearly basis in various scenarios.

Offshore wind has been identified as the **optimal power source** from among intermittent RES (solar PV, onshore wind, offshore wind).

- **Cost-competitive:** For the 2045 horizon, offshore wind appears to be more cost-competitive for the target profile than onshore wind, solar. Offshore wind turbines are larger, offshore wind farms have higher capacity and a higher load factor (the actual power generated divided by the theoretical maximum power production) than other RES and they do not contend with land scarcity (e.g., the ZAN law in France and the SdA regulation in Switzerland). In the basic setup considering electricity supply from off-shore wind sources only, energy costs would be in the 43 to 78 EUR/MWh range with about 60% of hourly matching for a baseload supply scenario.
- **Lower supply risk:** Offshore wind is considered a lower supply risk technology as it is characterized by a more stable production profile and it is more likely than other RES to produce power during hours when the market is short on power.
- **Simpler procurement:** Considering the size of typical state-of-the-art offshore wind farms in the GW range, only one or a few contracts would be needed to secure CERN's total energy need compared to signing 20+ PPAs with various onshore wind and solar PPA providers. This simplifies the procurement significantly.
- **CERN would be an attractive partner for offshore wind developers** in the context of the current allocation of seabed in France, mainly for two reasons:
 - The ability to contract well in advance of the commission date (typically 8 years before a windfarm begins to supply energy) would help offshore developers to come to a financial closure and secure attractive debt financing.
 - CERN, due to its reputation, would help developers get priority to obtain seabed to build offshore wind parks. Seabed could be an in-kind contribution to the developer providing that power would need to be contracted with CERN (at least up to CERN's need).
 - Offshore wind as power source would require buying missing and selling excess energy on the grid throughout the year – a common practice in the industry today – as the offshore wind generation profile will be different from CERN's required load (for instance selling 0.7 TWh and buying 0.7 TWh out of 1.7 TWh during different times in 2045). In total, during the 15 years of FCC-ee operations this could sum-up to approximately 12 TWh to be bought from the grid and 12 TWh to be sold to the grid.

CERN could further increase the level of hourly matching to 80% or 95% by **adding solar PV and onshore wind and battery storage** capacity (which would be more economical than simply adding more capacity from offshore wind to achieve the same level of hourly matching) and it would have the following implications:

- Increasing energy costs by 7 EUR/MWh to reach 80% of hourly matching and by 38 EUR/MWh to reach 95% without storage, based on today's market situation,
- Increasing financial risks as it will lead to overcapacity. CERN would receive more energy from the RES projects in total through a year and thus the amount of energy to be bought from and sold back to the grid increases (from 1.4 TWh in the base case to 1.5 TWh when reaching 80% and to 4 TWh when reaching 95%). This increases exposure to the wholesale market and the associated financial risk that market price could fall below the agreed PPA price at certain hours. It also permits CERN selling energy, though.

Technology mix summary (2/2)

Additionally, **contracting of clean storage capacity** (battery, that can typically store power for 2 to 6 hours, and other innovative long-duration energy storage that could store energy beyond 6 hours and up to approximately a week) could have several advantages:

- Reducing further financial risk for CERN (less need to purchase electricity from the market during low-supply periods),
- Making the power supply even more sustainable (increase the actual level of renewables in the supply mix),
- Incentivizing investments into new technologies needed for the energy transition (requiring not only green energy production but also flexible green energy),
- Further reducing energy costs by using energy from storage instead of from the grid when market prices are higher:
 - Battery storage with a capacity of about 200 MW would slightly increase the RES matching level to 65% and would slightly reduce energy costs by about 2 EUR per MWh.
 - Options with higher impacts are LDES technologies (e.g., flow batteries, scalable battery systems). These could offer up to one week of storage – and, as these technologies are still in development, they could continue to become significantly more effective and affordable until 2035. Following this route could potentially raise the RES matching level to 95% in a more cost-effective way: reaching 95% with the storage solution would cost about 15 EUR/MWh less than reaching 95% without the storage solution.

Load shifting was studied to potentially adapt the yearly schedule (e.g., changing the long maintenance break from winter to summer) and adapt the timing of beam operation during the day.

- Shifting the beam operation period to the winter season would increase the hourly RES matching based on offshore wind alone from 60% to 70%, but it would also increase energy cost by about 10 EUR/MWh. This option would be worth exploring if gains from providing recovered waste heat to consumers with main needs during winter can compensate the increase in power cost. Breakeven would be reached if the provided waste-heat market value reaches about 20 million EUR, excluding additional investments required by heat suppliers and public energy supply agencies to provide the heat.
- Adapting the beam operation during the day – for example, adapting the start and end times of physics operation would lead to a minor cost advantage of about 1 EUR/MWh, representing a gain of about 2 million EUR per year.

Technical feasibility and investment cost and trade-off vs. the potential benefits of storage and load flexibility need to be further studied (e.g., storage could enable further optimization that have not been sized and could further reduce the energy cost for CERN, choice of storage technology would impact cost and benefits).

A: To assess the optimal supply portfolio, several scenarios are defined

Base case – Grid sourcing only

Buy electricity from the grid

Approach 1 – Offsite RES

RES¹ PPA², with off-site 3rd party generation, residual from grid

Approach 2 – Offsite RES with 80% RES

RES¹ PPA², with off-site 3rd party generation and minimum 80% of source from renewable, residual from grid

Approach 3 – Offsite RES with 95% RES

RES¹ PPA², with off-site 3rd party generation and minimum 95% of source from renewable, residual from grid

Approach 4 – Offsite RES + Storage

RES¹ PPA², with off-site 3rd party generation, storage solution, residual from grid

Approach 5 – Offsite RES with load flexibility

RES¹ PPA², with off-site 3rd party generation, residual from grid and adapting the load profile

1. RES = Renewable Energy Sources, here Onshore Wind and Solar PV
 2. PPA = Power Purchasing Agreement, here assumed to be "pay as produced"

A: Overview of assumptions to assess technology mix

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

Category		CAPEX - 2035, EUR/kW	OPEX - 2035, EUR/kW/year	Energy price, EUR/MWh	Comments
PPA	Offshore wind	1,736	14	30	Energy price estimated from producer perspective, using Capex and Opex projection and including expected return of 5% on Capex and an additional margin of 4 EUR/MWh
	Onshore wind	1,020	26	39	
	Solar PV	433	9	34	
Wholesale market	Buy			60 (average)	Hourly price with average of 60 EUR/MWh – pre-energy crisis typical price level excluding inflation effect ¹
	Sell			Capped at 20	Capped market price to avoid over optimizing on profit that could be made from selling energy to the grid
Storage	Battery	330	3	n/a	

1. With a 3% inflation for ~20 years, actual power market price paid would be 100 EUR/MWh if actual market price are assumed to be 60 EUR/MWh

Some considerations

- **Energy price** includes only the **cost incurred per unit of energy acquired** by CERN from each source, any other kind of grid fees, imbalance cost or taxes are excluded
- **CAPEX** and **OPEX** projection **depends on numerous factors**, such as cost of elements, interest rate, inflation, etc. **Assumption taken** for those factors **will impact greatly the conclusion** of optimal procurement mix
- **For the simulation**, learning curve per technology is considered **to project CAPEX and OPEX** into the future, **other factors** like land acquisition, inflation **are not included**

A1-3: Increasing the requirement for green energy would increase energy cost and volumes to be bought and sold on the market

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

Detailed on the next pages ■ Solar ■ Onshore Wind ■ Offshore Wind ■ Power from the grid ■ Power to the grid

2045 VOLUMES

	Base case	Approach 1	Approach 2	Approach 3
Setup	Buy electricity from the grid	Off-site RES ¹ PPA, with no minimum of RES energy used to meet demand, residual from grid	Off-site RES ¹ PPA, with minimum 80% ² of RES energy used to meet demand, residual from grid	Off-site RES ¹ PPA, with minimum 95% ² of RES energy used to meet demand, residual from grid
Installed capacity, MW	0 0 0	0 0 349	344 0 422	598 822 497
Annual generation, TWh	0 0 0 1.7 0	0 0 1.7 0.7 -0.7	0.5 0 2.1 0.3 -1.2	0.9 2.2 2.4 0.1 -3.9
Energy cost³, EUR/MWh	Demand profile is leading to a lower average price than flat market price 49	43	50	81
Share of RES², %	0	61	80	95
Other considerations	Uncertainty on price level – 100% market exposure (1.7 TWh)	Market exposure of 1.4 TWh on day-ahead price	Market exposure of 1.5 TWh on day-ahead price	Market exposure of 4.0 TWh on day-ahead price

1. RES = Renewable Energy Sources, here Onshore Wind and Solar PV; 2. % of RES production from PPA that is used to meet the demand i.e., not sold back on the grid 3. As consumed cost of energy including adjustments with market and excluding any grid fees, imbalances fee, tax and inflation

A1: Sourcing energy, not covered directly by renewable PPA, from the grid will increase the energy cost by ~13 EUR/MWh

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION 2045 VOLUMES

1. excluding any grid fees, imbalances fee, tax and inflation

A1: During beam operation, more energy is needed from the grid to meet the required demand

2045 VOLUMES

— Load ■ Offshore wind ■ Power from the grid ■ Power to the grid

Overview of monthly energy demand and sourcing, GWh

Comments

In this scenario, as there is no requirement regarding the level of energy from RES PPA to be used directly, sourcing only from offshore wind is the most cost-competitive option to cover the energy needs of FCC

Demand not covered by offshore wind is bought from the grid – mainly when energy demand is the highest (this is during beam operation in summer)

During the downtime of FCC (winter), excess supply from offshore wind is sold back to the grid

This creates financial risks for CERN

A1: Offshore wind PPA price could be more expensive than onshore wind PPA if grid connection fee are added, and cost reduction is slower than expected

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

Rational

- Current projection for **offshore** wind's **capex are not including grid connections** (as RTE is currently taking charge of those costs for offshore wind project in France), and there will be **learning curves** that allow cost reduction
- Additionally, projected opex per kW for offshore wind are expected to decrease vs today and become lower per kW than for onshore wind as offshore wind turbines and farms are expected to become bigger and more dense less resources would be needed for **maintenance**,
- Alternative hypothesis for offshore wind is to assess the impact if cost decreases are less than currently anticipated

A1: Offshore wind could still be the preferred sourcing option, even with higher capex and opex assumption

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

2045 VOLUMES

Offshore wind Onshore wind

Take-aways

As result of optimizing with the alternative costs hypothesis, Onshore wind could have been considered a more cost-effective option (53 EUR/MWh vs 50 EUR/MWh if offshore wind was pursued with the revised cost hypothesis)

However, it would require more installed capacity (~+300 MW), as Onshore wind has lower capacity factor and more PPA would need to be contracted, as average installed capacity per project is lower for onshore wind than for offshore wind

Thus, offshore wind could still be considered as a valid option for CERN

1. Considering average size of 200-1000 MW for Offshore wind project, and 50 - 100 MW for Onshore wind
 2. excluding any grid fees, imbalances fee, tax and inflation

A1: For TT operation, higher capacity would need to be contracted but expected energy cost and share of RES would remain similar

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

■ Solar
 ■ Onshore Wind
 ■ Offshore Wind
 ■ Power from the grid
 ■ Power to the grid

1. RES = Renewable Energy Sources, here Onshore Wind and Solar PV;

2. excluding any grid fees, imbalances fee, tax and inflation

3. % of RES production from PPA that is used to meet the demand i.e., not sold back on the grid

A4: Different storage systems can be considered to help increase share of renewable power and reduce energy cost

Technology considered in this effort low high

Technology	Typical duration at full load, hours	Average round-trip efficiency, %	Expected Capex ¹ for 2035, EUR/kWh	Total capex required	Technology Maturity	Land & Site requirement	Rationale
Battery e.g., lithium-ion	~ 2 – 6	95	~100		Reduce the impact of dynamic behavior of FCC to the grid (200 MW change in seconds)		
LDES – up to 1 day e.g., air-metal or electrochemical flow batteries	~ 6 – 24	50 - 80	~25		Increase the usage of intermittent RES generation within a day (e.g., using RES production between beam operation for beam operation when load is maximum) which requires 8+ hours storage capacity		
LDES – up to 1 week e.g., power – heat/gas – power	~ 24 - 168	50 - 60	~15		Increase the usage of intermittent RES generation within a week when either lack of wind for a few days during beam operation or no beam operation for a few days due to a technical stop		
LDES – from weeks to months	> 168		Allows seasonal transfer of energy (e.g., to use RES production during long maintenance break during beam operation). But the amount of energy to store could be significant (40G Wh for 1 week of beam operation)				
Pump Storage Hydropower	~ 2 - 24 ²	70 - 90		Proven technology , but limited new development planned in France/Switzerland or need to identify existing capacity that could be contracted by CERN			

1. Average Capex considering configurations with typical ratio between charge/discharge power and energy storage size
 2. Typical size for commercial usage

A4: LDES help to reduce energy cost and financial risks when aiming for a higher share of renewable energy

1. Minimum RES share of 61% would archive even there is no requirement
 2. Two architypes of LDES are considered: duration up to 1 day and duration up to 1 week

A5: Overview of potential options to adapt CERN's demand profile, in order to further reduce the energy cost

ILLUSTRATIVE

Rationale **Change long maintenance break (e.g., summer break)**
Higher offshore wind production in winter

Adapt daily beam operation timing
Usually, higher offshore wind production in the evening and lower market prices during off-peak hours

Not assessed as not possible unless dumping the beam and thus downgrading the output of physic experiments

Decrease peak demand
Market price can peak on a few hours (e.g., +200 EUR/MWh in one hour)

Illustration

A5: Shifting shutdown to summer would allow higher share of RES but also have a higher energy cost

1. excluding any grid fees, imbalances fee, tax and inflation

Key takeaways

By shifting the annual shutdown from winter to summer, **energy cost would increase by 25%** (+11 EUR/MWh), driven by higher wholesale buying prices through the operation period

As offshore wind tends to produce more power during the winter than the summer, shifting the break from winter to summer would **increase the share of RES** directly used by CERN

A lifecycle analysis including energy storage, water cooling and waste heat supply is **required to be able to provide an answer** if operation in summer is more suitable than operation in winter.

A5: CERN could potentially save EUR 2 mn per year by adapting daily beam operation timing

ILLUSTRATIVE

— Power demand — Optimized power demand — Offshore wind generation — Power prices

Example of load adjustment

Assuming two cycles of 8h for full load beam operation within 24h, there are 4h¹ of flexibility

1. Over 24 hours of beam operation, is considered twice 8h of "physics beam operation" profile and twice 2h of "ready for beam" profile

By adjusting beam operation timeline, CERN could capture higher share of RES and reduce overall energy cost

Implementing an optimization system would require the **development of an algorithm** in CERN's operations

Assuming reliable price and weather forecasts 1 week ahead, 2045 power consumption level and only beam operation optimization, CERN could save **1 EUR/MWh** which would represent **EUR 2+ mn per year**

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- Technology mix

Procurement options

- Geography

Societal impact

Appendix

Procurement options summary

Several procurement options were studied. Aiming for a main supply from offshore wind and no particular requirement to achieve immediately a very high hourly RES coverage, all options involve a single, large transaction to secure the base supply needs (further increasing hourly RES coverage may either include additional supply demand within the single transaction or further PPAs):

- 1. Procurement of PPAs with equity participation**, where CERN would be a co-investor and an off-taker through a PPA "at-cost". This would result in securing power supply over a very long term at a lower price (4 EUR/MWh less than contracting a PPA without being an investor). While CERN would not build nor operate the RES project, CERN would bear some construction and operational risk as an investor.
- 2. Procurement through a base pre-FID PPA and a series of additional PPAs** linked to individual RES projects. CERN could then build the desired portfolio but would bear profile risks. By contracting pre-FID, it would enable a cost+ pricing which is more attractive than contracting post-FID.
- 3. Procurement of PPAs through an intermediary**, where CERN would benefit from a "full service" contract with a single party, who builds and manages the RES portfolio and manages the profile risk for CERN at a premium (about 5 to 10 EUR/MWh more than directly contracting a series of PPAs). This option is typically available from a limited set of large and diversified suppliers.

The **most suitable procurement option** for CERN is option 2: **PPA(s) pre-FID** with partnership(s), to enable the financing and secure the seabed(s). CERN would benefit from advantageous power prices, as it would make project development possible by:

- Securing long-term revenues for the developer before the financial closure of the project – a process so long that, for many potential off-takes, eight years can pass before the first generation of power is possible
- Procuring an advantage in securing the seabed, thanks to CERN's reputation and engagement to construct and operate a large research infrastructure with guaranteed long-term energy needs that represent a secured revenue for the supplier.

Alternatively, option 3 – procuring through an intermediary managing PPA portfolio and profile risks – could be considered to reduce financial uncertainties. Investing directly in a project – option 1 – is not recommended due to the construction and operational risks that CERN would bear in that case.

A PPA in the range of 15 years for the duration of the envisioned FCC-ee operation should be targeted. Contracts for a longer period do not lead to potentially lower costs, since a significant part of the RES project value can be secured through the initial 15 years. Contracts for a significantly shorter period would lead to not covering the entire envisioned FCC-ee operation period and potentially higher costs as financial security of the project would be reduced compared to a 15-year PPA.

B: Each procurement option has advantages and drawbacks

█ Better
 █ Intermediate
 █ Worse

	Description	B1 Energy cost	Financial / shape risk	Investment need	Feasibility
B2	Procurement of PPAs with equity participation CERN would invest equity (along with other partners) into RES project to secure the RES volume	█	█	█	█
B3	Procurement through a series of individual PPAs CERN would contract PPAs with different counterparties to create the desired portfolio mix	█	█	█	█
B4	Procurement of PPAs through an intermediary CERN would contract a full service with one counterparty who would decide the technology mix and take care of the shape risk	█	█	█	█

B1: Depending on the procurement approach, energy cost would vary

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

■ Flat profile ■ As consumed ■ Adjustment

Energy price, EUR/MWh

Energy price considered excluding any grid fees, imbalances fee, tax and inflation

B: Depending on the targeted technology mix, a portfolio of 1-30 PPAs would be required

1. Average capacity of PPA deals between 2018-2022

2. 50MW is considered as the average in line with PPA deals between 2018-2022

Implications

If CERN is procuring energy through a series of individual PPAs (**B3**) or through equity participation (**B2**), considering offshore wind project would help securing the required capacity while limiting the number of transactions

If CERN is procuring energy through an intermediary (**B4**), technology mix could be more diversified without having to manage several transactions

B2: CERN could consider investing in RES project to get lower PPA prices

ILLUSTRATIVE

From the project perspective, partnering with CERN could ease financing

- CERN could guaranty part of the volume off-take (reducing the need to identify other off-takers to take FID)
- CERN would directly contribute to the financing by investing before the project is built

From CERN perspective, a lower energy cost but with additional risks

- After amortization (e.g., 15 years) debt is reimbursed and CERN would own a part of the asset
- CERN would procure energy at a lower price (e.g., no/limited margin)
- From the investor's perspective, CERN would bear construction and operational risks (despite not building nor operating the asset)

B3: CERN could sign PPA at pre-FID stage to secure energy price at cost+

ILLUSTRATIVE

CERN could ease the research for financing

- CERN could contract a (very) long-term PPA (e.g., 15-20 years) ahead of time (e.g., 5 years before project starts producing power)
- CERN could be considered as a counterpart with a higher credit ratings than companies as an international organization

Advantages for CERN

- Securing a PPA would give visibility on the (very) long-term of energy costs
- Doing so pre-FID would enable cost+ pricing and reduce the impact on market conditions (e.g., value-based pricing in a high energy price environment)
- No construction nor operational risk for CERN
- Offsite energy storage can be included

B3: Physical PPAs involve a physical network connection allowing for direct power delivery but with greater price risk

Illustrative

A physical PPA is a power supply agreement by which...

- 1 A **corporate buyer** pays the agreed PPA price to the **power producer** and receives GoOs¹
- 2 Renewable electricity is delivered to **grid**
- 3 Renewable electricity is **supplied** to corporate facilities
- 4 **Corporate buyer** receives and pays for additional electricity via local retailer or contracted 3rd party

1. Guarantees of Origin certificates can be sold within a PPA or independently
2. The risk associated with the profile of intermittent generation, which might see lower revenues in the wholesale market due to cannibalization

Considerations when entering these contracts

Advantages

- **Direct delivery of power** via the system or market operator in the load location, given availability of **physical network connection** between load and asset
- **No accounting concerns** under IFRS
- Allows for **hedging** of a part of the **electricity consumptions**

Disadvantages

- Difficult to **find suppliers** that are willing to **do the energy management**
- Potential **cost increase in residual demand** due to that demand being mostly during hours when renewable production is low
- Exposes the buyer to **profile risk**²

B3: Most organizations would contract a virtual PPA instead of physical PPA

ILLUSTRATIVE

A virtual PPA is a pricing hedging tool by which...

- 1 Corporate buyer and power producer agree upon **net-settled virtual PPA price** (strike price) and corporate buyer can receive **GoOs**
- 2 **Producer** sells the electricity in the **wholesale power market** where asset is located
- 3 **Producer** receives payments from the **wholesale electricity market**, which are netsettled¹ against the PPA price agreed with the **corporate buyer**
- 4 **Corporate buyer** continues to **purchase electricity for its facilities** under its local contracts in the market where the load is located²

Examples of companies that signed virtual PPA

1. Each party in the agreement is subject to gains or losses depending on the outcome of the difference between the wholesale power price and the agreed upon PPA price
 2. As the virtual PPA contract is a financial settlement, a physical network connection between the generation asset(s) and the load is not necessary

Advantages

Geographic flexibility makes a broader range of options

- Allows for **hedging** of a part of the **electricity consumptions**
- Can be combined with standard physical power procurement on the market

Disadvantages

Exposes the buyer to **profile risk**

The buyer is having **decorrelation risk** when procuring outside of its bidding area

B3: Significant pre-deal work and specific in-house competences and capabilities are required to manage a portfolio of PPAs

■ PPA deal step ■ CERN internal process ■ RES construction¹

1. See project indicative timeline in appendix

B4: An intermediary can assemble and manage a portfolio of PPAs for CERN for a premium

Illustrative green power procurement set-up via an intermediary

Key elements to consider

- Total price **includes** premium for profile risk and flexibility
- Volume delivered **includes consumption flexibility** (e.g., what happens with sudden drop in demand due to loss of beam, flexibility to ramp-up)
- **Includes green guarantees** (e.g., guarantee of origin linked/not linked to existing capacity or linked to new projects)
- **Includes responsibilities** (e.g., profile risk, in case of force majeure event)
- **Is more expensive than management with in-house senior market-experienced team**

B4: First 24/7 green electricity PPAs picking up

VATTENFALL Microsoft

Vattenfall will deliver renewable energy 24/7 to Microsoft's Swedish DCs (Gävle, Sandviken and Staffans-torp) using the 24/7 Matching solution

- **Vattenfall will deliver** EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) labelled **hydro and wind power 24/7** to the three DCs in 2021
- With the 24/7 Matching solution, **Microsoft can track** both the datacenter **energy consumption** and the **renewable energy resource from Vattenfall's wind parks and hydro stations** on an hourly basis to ensure matching on-demand 24 hours a day, 365 days a year

- On a 10-year contract, AES will provide 500 MW renewable energy for Google's Virginia DCs ensuring 90% carbon-free energy
- AES bear the risk of under and over generation by purchasing and selling into the electricity market on an hourly basis as needed, while Google simply pays for their load at a stable \$/MWh
- By combining a diverse set of carbon-free energy resources and a battery that can shift generation hours, AES crafts a portfolio closely tied to Google's load to guarantee that DCs are powered by carbon-free energy 90% of the time¹

B4: Google purchases electricity from 23 renewable electricity projects in five German states

Case study – Google Engie deal

Context of the move

- **Google is one of the largest buyers of Corporate PPAs**, with a cumulative capacity of 6.6 GW as of Jan 2021
- **232 MW**, is the total PPA volume contracted between Engie and Google
- **This deal is part of a 1.6 GW renewable electricity purchase package** that Google announced, the biggest it has ever completed (of which 793 MW is purchased in Europe)

Google's industry margins limits the value in upstream integration

Breakdown of PPA deals

Engie will provide Google with 232 MW from several projects:

- **92 MW coming from its Belgian offshore wind park** Norther in the North Sea (2019 deal)
- **39 MW from German solar PV projects** scheduled to become operational in 2023 (2021 deal)
- **101 MW from life extensions of 22 existing wind parks** that no longer receive subsidy support, across five federal states (2021 deal)

Google's decarbonization goals

Short term target

- German facilities 80% carbon-free by 2022 on an hourly basis

Long term target

- Carbon Free Energy (CFE) for 2030, covering all data centers, cloud platforms and offices across the world

Track record:

- Signed 52 agreements to purchase nearly 5.5 gigawatts (GW) between 2010 and 2019

B4: BASF is investing substantially to produce own primary energy

Ludwigshafen plant requires 6 TWh / year

4 times the initial total CERN with FCC demand

a strategic topic for BASF
We create chemistry

B4: BASF to acquire 49.5% of the offshore wind farm Hollandse Kust Zuid (1.5 GW) from Vattenfall

General description

■ - BASF

We create chemistry

VATTENFALL

1.5 GW offshore wind farm Hollandse Kust Zuid (HKZ), COD 2023

Value proposition of major stakeholders

Secure supply to Antwerp Verbund site, Belgium and other European sites **with renewable electricity**

Apply low-emission technologies at several of its **production sites in Europe**

Enable an efficient use of capital by bringing in financial **co-investors**

Share the risks and benefits in realizing the **first subsidy-free wind farm** in the world in which **revenues are less certain**

Remain responsible for the **construction**, and later for the **management and maintenance** of the wind farm

Financing

Purchase price of EUR 0.3 bn with closing expected in **Q4 2021**

EUR 1.6 bn¹ initial total investment from BASF with plan to sell shares later

1. Including BASF's contribution to fund the wind farm construction

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- Technology mix
- Procurement options

Geography

Societal impact

Appendix

C: Power is best sourced first in France

Expected main source of procurement

Detailed on following pages

Location of production	Rational
On-site	Expected limited capacity (e.g., land availability) in regards of total energy need
C1 France	Existing reliable and high capacity connection to French grid Potential for development of new renewable capacity (especially for offshore wind) and government supportive of offshore wind project Reduced financial risks (e.g., decorrelation risks if not local) and risk on green accountability
Switzerland	Expected limited options for additional renewable capacity
C2 Germany	Procuring energy from Germany would either be more costly (e.g., building dedicated line, transmission costs between Germany and France) or increasing risks (e.g., uncertainties of availability of border transmission, decorrelation between day-ahead prices between France and Germany)

C1: Offshore wind is expected to have a momentum in the next years in France as it beneficiates from proper conditions and governmental support

French government supports offshore wind

Government objectives

- Minimal call for tender attribution of **2 GW per year**
- **x 5** offshore wind capacity by **2028** (5.2-6.2GW)
- **x 40** offshore wind capacity by **2050** (~40GW)

Financial incentives

- Call for tender, guarantying **medium term fixed selling price**
- Grid connection cost for all new projects under competitive process **taken by RTE¹**

Territory is suitable for the technology

- **2nd largest wind potential in Europe** after UK
- **5,000+ km of coast lines**
- **3 decorrelated wind regimes:** Mediterranean, English channel, Atlantic
- **Exploitable technical potential:** **90 TWh** for fixed technology (but 16 TWh dedicated to other usages) and **155 TWh** for floating technology (among 33 TWh accessible)

Some major players already positioned

- **2+ GW** under construction in Mediterranean and English channel areas
- **4+ GW** announced projects in the 3 areas

Example of active players in France:

1. French TSO (Réseau de Transport de l'Électricité)

C1: Today, offshore wind capacity is limited in France and government is supporting its development

Installed capacity in 2022

1. French grid operator (Réseaux de Transport de l'Électricité)

France objectives

- **X5** offshore wind capacity by **2028** (5.2-6.2GW)
- **X40** offshore wind capacity by **2050** (~40GW)
- French state committed to a minimal call for tender attribution of **2 GW per year**

Financial incentives

- Call for tender, guarantying medium term fixed selling price
- Grid connection cost for all new projects under competitive process taken by RTE¹

Potential pain points

- Limited social acceptance (e.g., Saint-Brieuc project)
- Technical, commercial and financial challenges (e.g., Groix et Belle-Ile abandoned project)

C1: 2+ GW of offshore wind capacity is under construction in France

Ongoing offshore wind projects in French coast

Project	Development Status	Operator	Commissioning Year	Net capacity, MW	Region
Saint-Brieuc	Under construction	Ailes Marines	2023	496	English Channel
Fécamp Off Shore	Under construction	Eolien Maritime France	2023	498	English Channel
Provence Grand Large	Under construction	EDF	2023	25	Mediterranean
Eoliennes Flottantes du Golfe du Lion	Under construction	Engie	2023	30	Mediterranean
EolMed	Under construction	BW Ideol	2023	30	Mediterranean
Courseulles-sur-Mer	Under construction	Eolien Maritime France	2024	448	English Channel
Le-Tréport	Under construction	EMDT	2025	496	English Channel
Noirmoutier	PPA signed	EMYN	2024	496	Atlantic
Dunkerque Offshore	FID		2027	500	English Channel
Cotentin offshore	Authorized		2028	1.000	English Channel
Belle île en Mer1	Bidding process		2030	250	Atlantic
Port-La-Nouvelle	Bidding process		2030	250	Mediterranean
Fos-sur-Mer	Bidding process		2030	250	Mediterranean
Oleron offshore wind	Announced			1.000	Atlantic
Belle île en Mer2	Announced			500	Atlantic
Fos-sur-Mer offshore	Authorized	EDF EN		26	Mediterranean

C1: International players are already positioned in the offshore French market

NOT EXHAUSTIVE

● Mediterranean ● Atlantic ● English Channel

Several players are active in wind offshore in France....

... And more players have expressed their willingness to enter the market

- “” Vattenfall prequalifies for upcoming Mediterranean offshore wind tender
VATTENFALL
- “” TotalEnergies, Corio Generation and Qair join forces to respond to a call for tenders in the Mediterranean
CORIO **TotalEnergies** **Qair**
- “” Océole – the partnership led by Equinor, prequalified for the call for tenders for the project of floating wind farms in the Mediterranean
equinor

C2: Supplying power from Germany would imply higher cost and uncertainties

	Options	Implications for the PPA buyer
 Physical supply	<p>A PPA is bought in Germany (RES connected to German grid) and energy is exported to France using existing interconnections between France and Germany</p>	<p>Uncertainty on the ability to export volumes (capacity subscription on an annual basis, at time border connection might be unavailable) and associated costs (capacity costs often evolve on a yearly basis)</p>
	<p>A PPA is bought in Germany (RES connected to German grid) and energy is exported by building a new transmission line (e.g., from around Basel to around Geneva)</p>	<p>Preliminary estimation of CAPEX required to build a new line could be 550-600 EUR mn or an additional 20-30 EUR/MWh cost Technical feasibility to build a new line through Switzerland / through the Jura would need to be assessed</p>
 Virtual supply	<p>A VPPA is bought in Germany and RES production is sold on the German market. Physical power supply is done on the French market and a financial transaction supply the Guarantees of Origin and the difference between German market price and aggregated PPA price</p>	<p>Risk of decorrelation between French and German markets would reduce financial predictability of energy supply cost – estimated impact could be ~10-20 EUR/MWh (depending on volume profile) or of 30-60 EUR mn/year for 2.6 TWh</p>

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Through the development of FCC, CERN will support the economy, accelerate the energy transition and technology advancement

1

Green energy procurement highly impacts the economy

Construction and operation of the wind farm would have direct (e.g., building and operating RES project) and indirect (e.g., suppliers of RES operator, services to employees of RES operator) impact on employment

Cascading consumption would positively impact local activities, would increase the global impact of the project evaluated at **EUR 400-700mn**

2

CERN would enable a project in line with energy transition objectives

Green electrification of the society

Europe is aiming to have an energy mix composed of **45%** of renewable energy by 2030

Power demand is expecting to increase to supply new needs (e.g., electric transportation) **+165 TWh per year** by 2050 in France

CERN would be aligned with these objectives by **generating additional 1.7+ TWh** of green energy per year with **~350-520 MW** of green energy developed

3

The project would participate to technology advancement

Offshore wind, high-capacity battery storage and LDES are technologies still relatively new by technical standards. CERN would participate to advance the technologies and help mastering the learning curve.

1: CERN would indirectly have a positive impact on economic health of the region

ILLUSTRATIVE

By procuring green energy for FCC operations, CERN would have an impact on the economy through direct, indirect and induced **employment** of 5-10k jobs which would cascade to **local consumption** stimulating **GDP growth**

Total economical impact of a 350-520 MW offshore wind project could be in the range of **EUR 400-700mn**

2: CERN would contribute to energy transition by boosting RES development and electrification

Supply
of power must rapidly
shift towards
renewables

45%

penetration of renewables in the overall EU energy mix by 2030¹ vs. 22% in 2021 (69% of electricity mix)

3-5X

annual RES installations in 2022-30 vs. 2018-20² to reach 1200+ GW

-55%

reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to 1990

Demand
for electricity will
increase as sectors
decarbonize

+165

TWh (+35%) electricity demand in France by 2050 vs. 2019

Including

+85

TWh in transport sector

and

+65

TWh in industrial sector

CERN's contribution

CERN would enable offshore wind farm development by **providing long term** (up to 2060) **forecasted power demand** which reduces cash flow uncertainties and therefore the barriers to secure financing and to develop the project.

3+mn tons CO2 eq. emission avoided during FCC operation period in comparison to market procurement³

Additional ~520+ MW renewable capacity.

By piloting high-capacity battery storage, CERN could become Europe's largest battery and accelerate the energy storage deployment in Europe.

1. RePowerEU
2. Solar PV ~x5, Onshore Wind ~x4 (including Repowering), Offshore Wind ~3
3. Considering the average carbon intensity of electricity in France in 2022

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Summary of energy cost per scenario

EUR/MWh, all estimates conservative and based on 2022 prices and technologies

2022 AS PRICE BASIS - 2035 FIGURES NOT ADJUSTED FOR INFLATION

	Base case	Approach 1	Approach 2	Approach 3	Approach 4.2	Approach 4.3	Risk assessment
Setup	Buy electricity from the grid	Off-site RES PPA , residual from grid	Off-site RES PPA , with minimum 80%² RES energy , residual from grid, no storage	Off-site RES PPA , with minimum 95%² RES energy , residual from grid	Off-site RES PPA , storage solution and minimum 80%² RES energy , residual from grid	Off-site RES PPA , storage solution and minimum 95%² RES energy , residual from grid	
Procurement of PPAs with equity participation	~ 49	~ 39 - 49	~ 46 - 56	~ 77 - 87	~ 45 - 55	~ 61 - 71	Require up-front investment with construction and operation risks
Procurement through a series of individual PPAs		~ 43 - 53	~ 50 - 60	~ 81 - 91	~ 49 - 59	~ 65 - 75	No up-front investment without construction and operation risks but profile risks
Procurement of PPAs through an intermediary		~ 48 - 63	~ 55 - 70	~ 86 - 101	~ 54 - 69	~ 70 - 85	No up-front investment without construction and operation risks nor profile risks
Market risk assessment¹ (1 = lowest risk, 6 = highest risk)	5	2	4	6	3	1	

1. Based on volume sold/bought on the market,
2. Level of energy from RES production used to meet the demand (either directly or through storage) – i.e., not sold back on the grid

Hourly matching of demand with RES production has more constraints than yearly matching

ILLUSTRATIVE

— RES Production — Demand ■ Directly used

RES production and demand profile

Level of renewable sourced

	Definition	Level (example)
Aggregated view	Total volume produced by RES / total volume needed	100%
Consumed view (grey area)	Share of RES production actually used to meet demand	68%

As the **ARENH tariff will end by 2025**, the baseline case scenario for CERN would be to source 100% of the volumes from the French grid

Current sourcing approach

CERN signed an **agreement with EDF** after a tender process

70-80% of CERN's consumed power is paid at **ARENH price** (42 EUR/MWh), and remaining volumes at market prices (by 12 "clicks")

Full flexibility on the contract (no "take-or-pay") and no flexibility premium – CERN has full visibility on the maximum load required and can adjust when ramping-up. However, downward changes of ~200 MW can happen unexpectedly (loss of beam)

'Default' approach after the end of ARENH will have a 100% market exposure with high risks

Power sourcing characteristics

Implications

Contract energy supply through an energy provider as a result of a tender

Potential premium for the need for downward flexibility

Up to 3 years contracts with a fixed price based on market price in France

Cost level would depend on market price with visibility only on the next few years (as opposed to the next 20 years)

No guaranty of origin regarding power

Scope 2 emissions will depend on the pace of decarbonization of the French grid

Power price in France increased over the last months

— French electricity market price — Forward as of Jan. 9th 2023 — ARENH

Power price in France, EUR/MWh

ARENH is a French governmental process, up to **100 TWh of nuclear power** are sold at **42 EUR/MWh** each year, up to 2025

Based on current forward prices in France:

- market prices are expected to remain high (above 100 EUR/MWh) for the next years
- Despite the backwardation, market prices are not expected to reach back their pre-crisis level by 2028

A: For this study, a digital twin of the physical energy system was built to optimize sizing of instruments, given granular hourly variability

ILLUSTRATIVE

1. e.g., unit dispatch, storage charge/discharge. | 2. e.g., hourly energy balance; asset min/max nominal power

The model has...

...an explicit, physical energy system as a graph-based linear optimal power flow model to represent energy conservation and conversion laws

...hourly variability in generation (RES capacity factors) and load

...inter-temporal shifting via storage charge and discharge

The optimization algorithm...

...derives optimal instrument sizing based on total system annualized costs

...considers hourly operational decisions¹

...enforces hourly and aggregate system constraints²

A4: There is a range of long-duration energy storage technologies being explored (1/2)

Thermal

Store energy thermally to release electricity and heat (e.g., sterling engines, molten salt)

Mechanical

Store gravitational potential or kinetic energy (e.g., PSH, gravity based, CAES, LAES, Liquid CO₂)

Chemical

Store energy in chemical bonds (e.g., H₂, power to gas to power)

Electrochemical

Batteries of different chemistries that store electrical potential energy (e.g., air-metal, flow batteries)

A4: There is a range of long-duration energy storage technologies being explored (2/2)

NOT EXHAUSTIVE

Type of storage	Storage technology	Description	Risk/Tech. maturity	Technical flexibility	Cost sensitivity	Performance RTE ²	Scalability
Chemical	Conventional (lead based)	Lead and/or lead dioxide-based batteries mainly used in the automotive industry	●	●	●	80-90%	●
	① Li-ion	Lithium is based battery extensively used in Consumer Electronics (CE) and Electric Vehicles (EV)	●	●	●	85-95%	●
	Flow — Vanadium redox	Two different electrolyte flows pass carbon-plastic composite electrodes in two compartments. Vanadium redox chemical base	●	●	●	70-80%	●
	② Flow —other ¹	Two different electrolyte flows pass carbon-plastic composite electrodes in two compartments. Other chemical bases	●	●	●	50-80%	●
	③ Hydrogen	Power to hydrogen conversion (e.g., using electrolysis) for use in power-to-power storage or other H2 applications	●	●	●	20-35%	●
Thermal	Future Li-based batteries	Post Li-ion technologies (e.g., Lithium-Sulphur, Lithium-Air)	●	●	●	TBD	●
	Molten salt	Low-cost, high-capacity battery that stores energy using molten elemental sodium and Sulphur	●	●	●	50-60%	●
	Thermal hydro	Use of temperature gradient to create power combined with large-scale heat and cold storage	●	●	●	80-90%	TBC
Electrical/Magnetic	Super capacitors	Electrochemical capacitors with high energy density; still experimental for large scale applications	●	●	●	85-95%	●
	Super conducting magnets (SMES)	Store energy in a magnetic field of a cryogenically cooled superconducting coil; still experimental	●	●	●	85-95%	●
Mechanical	Pumped hydro (PHES)	Moves water between reservoirs at different elevations (-100GW installed worldwide); geographically limited	●	●	●	75-85%	●
	Gravity based	Stores potential energy by moving large blocks of concrete using cranes and wires from high platforms	●	●	●	75-85%	●
	Flywheel ³	Stores kinetic energy with a rotor spinning at high speeds; particularly adapted for high frequency usage	●	●	●	80-90%	●
	Compressed air (CAES)	Stores energy in compressed air. Relatively low efficiency, combined with CCGT. 2 installations exists and pilots with new technologies are currently under development	●	●	●	50-70%	●
Cryogenic	Cryogenic storage	Stores energy in liquid air/nitrogen that is heated to drive a turbine when electricity is needed	●	●	●	50-70%	●

① Given its maturity and, Li-ion has the potential to be cost competitive in the 6h range by 2030, beyond its typical short duration (1 Ah) application. Its bankability also allows for large-scale pilots .

② Flow batteries have competitive cost trajectories at long durations (due to electrolyte abundance), and vanadium redox flow batteries are more mature than other flow technologies

③ Hydrogen is constrained by roundtrip efficiency in the near-term though expected reductions in electrolyzer cost could make it a cost-competitive technology

1. Roundtrip efficiency 2. Includes Zinc-iron; Zinc-bromide and Hydrogen Bromide 3. Largest Flywheel producer Beacon Power bankrupt in 2011

A5: In France, power prices and offshore wind generation tend to be higher during winter, even if more electricity from offshore is produced during winter

Offshore wind generation profile¹
%

Day-ahead price in France in 2019
EUR/MWh

1. Theoretical offshore wind generation in 2019 on the French Atlantic coast of a 1kW capacity turbine